

Supplementary Material S3 – Answers to the stakeholder survey

A - Collection of answers received during the stakeholder workshop held within the Austrian COMET module *FuLIBatteR* in autumn 2023 (Leoben, Austria). N=21.

4. Do you have work related experience in sustainability or environmental management?

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- Yes 17
- No 4

5. Which domain can your company be assigned to?

[Weitere Informationen](#)

- Public sector 0
- Research institute 12
- Private company 4
- Listed company 5

6. Which industry can your company be assigned to? (e.g. manufacturing, recycling, IT,...)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

21
Antworten

Neueste Antworten
"recycling"
"Research"
"Research and development"
...

5 Befragten (24%) antworteten Research für diese Frage.

7. According to the given definition, is your company or institution considered as micro, small, medium or large?

[Weitere Informationen](#)

- Micro 0
- Small 2
- Medium 8
- Large 11

8. How many employees are exclusively involved in sustainability or environmental management in full time equivalents? [Weitere Informationen](#)

None.	0
< 1	1
1-2	0
3-5	1
> 5	19

9. To what extent do you agree with the following statement:
The company or institution I work for is already extensively involved in environmental and sustainability issues. [Weitere Informationen](#)

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

Sustainability commitment

10. To what extent do you associate the following keywords with a positive outcome (chance) of successful sustainability management? (Part 1 of 5) [Weitere Informationen](#)

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

Cope with climate change

Promote social equity

Saving Energy

Energy Security

Saving resources

11. To what extent do you associate the following keywords with successful sustainability management? (Part 2 of 5) [Weitere Informationen](#)

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

Secure resource supply

Affordable resources

Reduction of environmental impacts

Waste reduction

Reduction of greenhouse gas

12. To what extent do you associate the following keywords with successful sustainability management? (Part 3 of 5) [Weitere Informationen](#)

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

Create new business models

Create jobs

Generate profit

Less disposal costs

New technologies

13. To what extent do you associate the following keywords with successful sustainability management? (Part 4 of 5)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● Strongly disagree ● Disagree ● Neutral ● Agree ● Strongly agree

14. To what extent do you associate the following keywords with successful sustainability management? (Part 5 of 5)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● Strongly disagree ● Disagree ● Neutral ● Agree ● Strongly agree

15. In your personal opinion, how would you rate the potential **positive impact** on businesses and the **implementation effort** of the listed keywords for successful sustainability management? (Part 1 of 5)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● Low effort, weak impact ● Low effort, high impact ● High effort, weak impact ● High effort, high impact

16. In your personal opinion, how would you rate the potential **positive impact** on businesses and the **implementation effort** of the listed keywords for successful sustainability management? (Part 2 of 5)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● Low effort, weak impact ● Low effort, high impact ● High effort, weak impact ● High effort, high impact

17. In your personal opinion, how would you rate the potential **positive impact** on businesses and the **implementation effort** of the listed keywords for successful sustainability management? (Part 3 of 5)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● Low effort, weak impact ● Low effort, high impact ● High effort, weak impact ● High effort, high impact

18. In your personal opinion, how would you rate the potential **positive impact** on businesses and the **implementation effort** of the listed key words to successfully address them in sustainability management? (Part 4 of 5)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● Low effort, weak impact ● Low effort, high impact ● High effort, weak impact ● High effort, high impact

19. In your personal opinion, how would you rate the potential **positive impact** on businesses and the **implementation effort** of the listed key words for successful sustainability management? (Part 5 of 5)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● Low effort, weak impact ● Low effort, high impact ● High effort, weak impact ● High effort, high impact

20. To which five chances do you yourself attribute the most (untapped) potential in your company?

[Weitere Informationen](#)

21. To what degree do you agree with the following statement:
The company I work for should take more action towards sustainability.

[Weitere Informationen](#)

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

Call to action

22. Do you want to point out anything with regard to chances we did not cover yet?

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4
Antworten

Neueste Antworten
...

23. To what degree do you associate the following keywords with risks of not implementing any kind of sustainability management? (Part 1 of 4)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● Strongly disagree ● Disagree ● Neutral ● Agree ● Strongly agree

24. To what degree do you associate the following keywords with risks of not implementing any kind of sustainability management? (Part 2 of 4)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● Strongly disagree ● Disagree ● Neutral ● Agree ● Strongly agree

25. To what degree do you associate the following keywords with risks of not implementing any kind of sustainability management? (Part 3 of 4)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● Strongly disagree ● Disagree ● Neutral ● Agree ● Strongly agree

26. To what degree do you associate the following keywords with risks of not implementing any kind of sustainability management? (Part 4 of 4)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● Strongly disagree ● Disagree ● Neutral ● Agree ● Strongly agree

27. How do you personally assess the following list of risks for your company? For a definition of the terms low, medium, high and critical please consult the attached graphic. (Part 1 of 2)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● Low ● Medium ● High ● Critical

28. How do you personally assess the following list of risks for your company? For a definition of the terms low, medium, high and critical please consult the attached graphic. (Part 2 of 2)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● Low ● Medium ● High ● Critical

29. To which five risks do you personally attribute the greatest potential for future damage to your company?

[Weitere Informationen](#)

Loss of ability to innovate	11
Loss of know-how	11
Loss of power	0
Liability risk	1
Benefit loss	3
Risk to human health and work force	4
Environmental impacts	7
Loss of licence to operate	2
Production downtime	1
Unaddressed deficiencies	4
Energy scarcity	3
Non-social behaviour e.g. sabotage	1
Image loss	9
Market loss	8
Project failure	10
Non-compliance	1
Loss of financing	12
Supply chain failure	2
Increasing costs	5
Uncertainty	6
Dependency	4

30. How do you rate the hindering effect of the following **internal barriers**? (Part 1 of 2)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

None Minor Medium High Very High

- Lack of standards and frameworks
- Lack of know-how
- Uncertainty of effects of measures
- Complexity of systems
- Interdisciplinarity
- Establishing Transparency
- Performance monitoring
- Spatial isolation of company
- No policy with regard on how to handle trade-offs
- No (reliable) data
- Capital in fixed assets (e.g. plants)
- (Incorrect) Risk perception
- Green washing
- Lack of (green) technology
- Scope and limits of existing methods
- Lack of comparability and benchmarks

31. How do you rate the hindering effect of the following **internal barriers**? (Part 2 of 2)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● None ● Minor ● Medium ● High ● Very High

32. To which **five internal barriers** to sustainability do you personally attribute the greatest challenge for your company?

[Weitere Informationen](#)

33. How do you personally rate the positive effect on sustainability (economically, ecologically or social) of the following **internal enablers**? (Part 1 of 2)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● None ● Minor ● Medium ● High ● Very High

- New business models, e.g. product-as-a-Service thinking
- Preference for renewable resources and energy
- Evidence-based decision making
- Mindset and awareness of management
- Promotion of awareness among employees
- Promotion of risk literacy
- Sustainability policy with set priorities
- Stakeholder integration
- Internal knowledge and data exchange
- Revisioning of processes
- Established transparency of processes
- Ecodesign of products

34. How do you personally rate the positive effect on sustainability (economically, ecologically or social) of the following **internal enablers**? (Part 2 of 2)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● None ● Minor ● Medium ● High ● Very High

- Industry-wide cooperation and network
- Establishment of frame-works and standards
- Know-how on tools and methods
- (Sustainable) Supply chain management
- Benchmarks
- Best practices
- Financing and resources
- Risk management
- Use of key performance indicators
- Invest in research and development

35. To which **five internal enablers** to sustainability do you personally attribute the greatest driving potential for your company?

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B - Collection of answers received during the presentation of preliminary results of the survey in autumn 2023 at the Sardinia Symposium (Cagliari, Italy). N=5.

1. Man [Weitere Informationen](#)

Woman	2
Man	3
Other	0

60%	40%
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2. What is your age? [Weitere Informationen](#)

18-24	0
25-34	1
35-44	3
45-54	0
54+	1

20%	20%	60%
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3. What is your position and job description? [Weitere Informationen](#)

5 Antworten

Neueste Antworten

"Research in energy and circular economy"
"Associate professor"
"Univ.Ass. at a technical university. Teaching and research in mechanical process tec..."
...

4. Do you have work related experience in sustainability or environmental management? [Weitere Informationen](#)

Yes	5
No	0

100%

5. Which domain can your company be assigned to?

[Weitere Informationen](#)

Public sector	1
Research institute	4
Private company	0
Listed company	0

6. Which industry can your company be assigned to? (e.g. manufacturing, recycling, IT,...)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

5
Antworten

Neueste Antworten
"Mechanical engineering"
"University"
"chemical/process engineering, recycling"
...

7. According to the given definition, is your company or institution considered as micro, small, medium or large?

[Weitere Informationen](#)

Micro	0
Small	1
Medium	2
Large	2

8. How many employees are exclusively involved in sustainability or environmental management in full time equivalents?

[Weitere Informationen](#)

None	1
1-2	0
3-5	0
> 5	4

9. To what degree do you agree with the following statement:

The company or institution I work for is already extensively involved in environmental and sustainability issues.

[Weitere Informationen](#)

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

Sustainability commitment

10. To which five chances do you yourself attribute the most (untapped) potential in your company?

[Weitere Informationen](#)

11. To which five risks do you personally attribute the greatest potential for future damage to your company?

[Weitere Informationen](#)

- Loss of ability to innovate 2
- Loss of know-how 3
- Loss of power 2
- Liability risk 0
- Benefit loss 0
- Risk to human health and work force 1
- Environmental impacts 0
- Loss of licence to operate 0
- Production downtime 0
- Unaddressed deficiencies 2
- Energy scarcity 2
- Non-social behaviour e.g. sabotage 0
- Image loss 2
- Market loss 1
- Project failure 1
- Non-compliance 0
- Loss of financing 4
- Supply chain failure 1
- Increasing costs 1
- Uncertainty 1
- Dependency 2

12. How do you rate the hindering effect of the following internal barriers to responsible production? (Part 1 of 2)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

- None
- Minor
- Medium
- High
- Very High

- New business models, e.g. product-as-a-Service thinking
- Preference for renewable resources and energy
- Evidence-based decision making
- Mindset and awareness of management
- Promotion of awareness among employees
- Promotion of risk literacy
- Sustainability policy with set priorities
- Stakeholder integration
- Internal knowledge and data exchange
- Revisioning of processes
- Established transparency of processes
- Ecodesign of products

13. How do you **rate the hindering effect** of the following internal barriers to **responsible production**? (Part 2 of 2)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● None ● Minor ● Medium ● High ● Very High

14. To which **five internal barriers** to sustainability do you personally attribute the greatest challenge for your company? [Weitere Informationen](#)

15. To what degree do you agree with the following statement:
The company I work for should take more action towards sustainability. [Weitere Informationen](#)

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

Call to action

16. How do you personally **rate the positive effect** on sustainability (economically, ecologically or social) of the following internal enablers? (Part 1 of 2)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● None ● Minor ● Medium ● High ● Very High

17. How do you personally **rate the positive effect** on sustainability (economically, ecologically or social) of the following internal enablers? (Part 2 of 2)

[Weitere Informationen](#)

● None ● Minor ● Medium ● High

18. To which **five internal enablers** to sustainability do you personally attribute the greatest driving potential for your company?

[Weitere Informationen](#)

- New business models, e.g. product-as-a-service 0
- Preference for renewable resources and energy 0
- Evidence-based decision making 1
- Sustainability mindset and awareness of management 1
- Promotion of risk literacy 0
- Sustainability policy with set priorities 0
- Stakeholder integration 0
- Internal knowledge and data exchange 0
- Revisioning of processes 0
- Established transparency of processes 0
- Edocdesign of products 0
- Know-how of experts 2
- Industry-wide cooperation and network 0
- Establishment of frameworks and standards 0
- Know-how on tools and methods 0
- (Sustainable) Supply chain management 0
- (Green) Technology 0
- Benchmarks 0
- Best practices 0
- Financing and resources 1
- Risk management 0
- Use of sustainability related key performance indicators 0
- Investment in research and development 0

